

19. Uluslararası Eğitim Camiası Sempozyumu Tam Metinleri

كتاب المتون الكاملة المؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للمجتمع التربوي

Book of Proceedings The 19th International Symposium of the Educational Community

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Said Assil, Sami Baskın, Esat Layek

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ÖN SÖZ

4–8 Kasım 2025 tarihlerinde Antalya’da gerçekleştirilen 19. Uluslararası Eğitim Camiası Sempozyumu, Saybilder Topluluğu’nun koordinasyonunda; Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi (Türkiye) ve Carthage Üniversitesi (Tunus) akademik desteğiyle başarıyla tamamlanmıştır. Eğitim bilimlerinin güncel gelişmelerini, yenilikçi yaklaşımlarını ve disiplinler arası etkileşimlerini ele alan bu sempozyum, uluslararası akademik dayanışmanın güçlü bir örneğini ortaya koymuştur.

Bu yılki sempozyumda Türkiye’den 45 bildiri; Almanya, Cezayir, Fas, Irak, Kuveyt, Mısır, Sudan, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı, Tunus, Umman ve Ürdün başta olmak üzere 11 farklı ülkeden de toplam 60 bildiri olmak üzere toplam 105 bildiri sunulmuştur. Bu çeşitlilik, hem kültürlerarası akademik alışverişi zenginleştirmiş hem de farklı eğitim sistemlerinin sorunlarının ve çözüm yollarının karşılaştırmalı olarak tartışılmasına imkân sağlamıştır.

Sempozyumun temel amacı, eğitim alanındaki araştırmaları uluslararası düzeyde görünür kılmak, yeni iş birliklerine zemin hazırlamak ve öğretim süreçlerine katkı sağlayacak bilimsel üretimi teşvik etmektir. Sunulan çalışmalar; eğitim teknolojileri, öğretmen eğitimi, dijital pedagojiler, dil öğretimi, psikolojik danışmanlık, özel eğitim, sürdürülebilir eğitim politikaları ve toplumsal dönüşüm gibi geniş bir yelpazeye yayılmıştır. Bu yönüyle sempozyum hem teorik hem de uygulamalı araştırmalar açısından güçlü bir bilgi birikimi ortaya koymuştur.

Bu kitap, sempozyumda sunulan çalışmaların tam metinlerinin bir araya getirilmesiyle oluşturulmuştur. Bununla birlikte kitap, yalnızca bildirilerin bir toplamı değil; farklı kültürlerden, dillerden ve akademik geleneklerden gelen bilim insanlarının ortak aklını yansıtan bir başvuru kaynağı niteliğindedir. Kitapta yer alan araştırmaların, eğitim bilimleri alanındaki uygulayıcılara, politika geliştiricilere ve araştırmacılara ilham verecek yeni perspektifler sunması hedeflenmektedir.

Sempozyumdan çıkan en önemli sonuçlardan biri, uluslararası akademik iş birliğinin eğitsel gelişime doğrudan katkıda bulunduğu bir kez daha görülmesidir. Farklı ülkelerden araştırmacıların ortaya koyduğu deneyimler ve çözüm önerileri, eğitimde karşılaşılan ortak sorunlara karşı daha bütüncül bakabilmemizi sağlamıştır. Ayrıca etkinlik sürecinde kurulan yeni bağlantılar, ilerleyen dönemlerde ortak projelerin ve yayınların hazırlığı açısından önemli bir başlangıç oluşturmuştur.

Bu bağlamda, eğitim bilimlerine gönül veren tüm akademisyenlere şu öneriler özellikle vurgulanmalıdır:

1. Disiplinlerarası araştırmalara daha fazla yer verilmesi, sorunların bütüncül biçimde anlaşılmasına katkı sağlayacaktır.
2. Uluslararası akademik iş birliklerinin artırılması, araştırma kalitesini ve etki alanını genişletecektir.
3. Dijitalleşme ve yapay zekâ temelli araştırmalara yatırım yapılması, geleceğin öğrenme süreçlerinin daha sağlıklı kurgulanmasına olanak tanıyacaktır.
4. Akademisyenlerin saha araştırmalarını desteklemesi, eğitim politikalarının daha gerçekçi temellere dayanmasına yardımcı olacaktır.
5. Genç araştırmacıların bilimsel üretime dahil edilmesi, akademik sürdürülebilirlik açısından büyük önem taşımaktadır.

Sonuç olarak, 19. Uluslararası Eğitim Camiası Sempozyumu'nun ortaya koyduğu bilgi birikimi, eğitim alanında çalışan tüm araştırmacılar için önemli bir kaynak oluşturmaktadır. Bu sempozyuma katkı sunan tüm bilim insanlarına, organizasyon sürecine emek veren akademik ve idari ekiplere ve eğitime gönül veren herkese içten teşekkürlerimizi sunarız. Bu kitabın, eğitim araştırmalarına yön veren değerli bir başvuru kaynağı olması temennisiyle...

Prof. Dr. Sami Baskın
Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

Preface

The 19th *International Education Community Symposium*, held in Antalya between 4–8 November 2025 under the coordination of the Saybilder Community, was successfully completed with the academic support of Mardin Artuklu University (Türkiye) and Carthage University (Tunisia). Addressing the latest developments in educational sciences, innovative approaches, and interdisciplinary interactions, this symposium presented a strong example of international academic solidarity.

This year, 45 papers from Türkiye and 60 papers from 11 different countries—including Germany, Algeria, Morocco, Iraq, Kuwait, Egypt, Sudan, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Tunisia, Oman, and Jordan—were presented, making a total of 105 academic contributions. This diversity enriched cross-cultural academic exchange and enabled comparative discussions on the challenges and solutions of various educational systems.

The primary purpose of the symposium was to enhance the international visibility of research in the field of education, create a platform for new collaborations, and promote scientific production that supports teaching and learning processes. The presented studies covered a wide range of fields, including educational technologies, teacher education, digital pedagogies, language teaching, psychological counseling, special education, sustainable education policies, and social transformation. In this regard, the symposium offered a strong knowledge base for both theoretical and applied research.

This book has been prepared by compiling the full texts of the studies presented at the symposium. It is not merely a collection of papers; rather, it serves as a reference source that reflects the collective intellectual contributions of scholars from different cultures, languages, and academic traditions. It is our expectation that the research in this volume will provide new perspectives for practitioners, policy makers, and researchers in the field of educational sciences.

One of the significant outcomes of the symposium is the reaffirmation that international academic cooperation directly contributes to educational development. The experiences and solutions shared by researchers from various countries allowed us to view common educational challenges from a more holistic perspective. Moreover, the new academic connections established during the event laid the foundation for future joint projects and publications.

In this context, we emphasize the following recommendations for all scholars dedicated to educational sciences:

1. Increasing interdisciplinary research will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of educational issues.
2. Expanding international academic cooperation will enhance research quality and impact.
3. Investing in digitalization and artificial intelligence–based studies will facilitate healthier designs of future learning processes.
4. Supporting field-based research will help ground educational policies in more realistic foundations.
5. Including young researchers in academic production is essential for long-term academic sustainability.

In conclusion, the knowledge generated through the 19th International Education Community Symposium constitutes a valuable resource for all researchers working in the field of education. We extend our sincere gratitude to all scholars who contributed to this symposium, to the academic and administrative teams involved in the organizational process, and to everyone devoted to education. We hope that this book becomes an influential reference source guiding future educational research.

Prof. Dr. Sami Baskin
Chair of the Organizing Committee

المقدمة

لقد اختتم بنجاح المؤتمر التاسع عشر للجالية التربوية الدولية الذي عُقد في مدينة أنطاليا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، بتنظيم من مجتمع سايبيلدر، وبدعم أكاديمي من جامعة ماردين أرتوكلو (تركيا) وجامعة قرطاج (تونس). وقد تناول هذا المؤتمر أحدث التطورات في علوم التربية والمقاربات المبتكرة والتفاعلات البيئية، مقدّمًا نموذجًا قويًا للتضامن الأكاديمي الدولي.

شارك هذا العام 45 باحثًا من تركيا و 60 باحثًا من 11 دولة—من بينها ألمانيا، الجزائر، المغرب، العراق، الكويت، مصر، السودان، المملكة العربية السعودية، تونس، عُمان، والأردن—ليصل العدد الإجمالي إلى 105 بحوث. وقد أسهم هذا التنوع في إثراء التبادل الأكاديمي بين الثقافات، وفي إتاحة الفرصة لمناقشة المشكلات والتصورات التربوية في مختلف الأنظمة التعليمية من منظور مقارن.

كان الهدف الرئيس من هذا المؤتمر هو تعزيز الحضور الدولي للأبحاث التربوية، وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي، وتشجيع الإنتاج العلمي الداعم لعمليات التعلم والتعليم. وقد شملت البحوث المقدمة مجالات واسعة مثل تكنولوجيا التعليم، تكوين المعلمين، البيداغوجيا الرقمية، تعليم اللغات، الإرشاد النفسي، التربية الخاصة، السياسات التربوية المستدامة والتحويلات الاجتماعية. ومن ثم، فقد قدّم المؤتمر رصيدًا معرفيًا قويًا للبحوث النظرية والتطبيقية على حد سواء.

أعدّ هذا الكتاب من خلال جمع النصوص الكاملة للأبحاث التي قدّمت في المؤتمر. وهو ليس مجرد تجميع للأوراق العلمية، بل يعدّ مرجعًا يعكس الفكر الجماعي للباحثين من ثقافات ولغات وتقاليد أكاديمية مختلفة. ونأمل أن تقدّم الدراسات الواردة فيه آفاقًا جديدة للباحثين والممارسين وصانعي السياسات في مجال علوم التربية.

ومن أبرز نتائج المؤتمر التأكيد من جديد على أن التعاون الأكاديمي الدولي يساهم مباشرة في تطوير العملية التعليمية. فقد أتاحت الخبرات والحلول التي قدّمها الباحثون من مختلف الدول رؤية أكثر شمولًا للتحديات المشتركة في التعليم. كما أسهمت العلاقات العلمية الجديدة التي نشأت خلال المؤتمر في تهيئة أرضية لمشاريع مشتركة وإصدارات علمية مستقبلية.

وفي هذا السياق، نؤكد على التوصيات الآتية للباحثين المهتمين بعلوم التربية:

1. توسيع نطاق البحوث البين-تخصصية لما لها من دور في فهم القضايا التربوية فهمًا تكامليًا.
2. تعزيز التعاون الأكاديمي الدولي بما يساهم في رفع جودة البحث العلمي وتوسيع أثره.
3. تشجيع الدراسات المتعلقة بالرقمنة والذكاء الاصطناعي لتصميم عمليات تعلم مستقبلية أكثر فعالية.
4. دعم البحوث الميدانية لترسيخ السياسات التعليمية على أسس أكثر واقعية.
5. إشراك الباحثين الشباب في الإنتاج العلمي ضمانًا لاستدامة العمل الأكاديمي.

ختامًا، يمثّل الرصيد المعرفي الذي أسفر عنه المؤتمر التاسع عشر للجالية التربوية الدولية مصدرًا مهمًا لكل الباحثين في مجال التعليم. ونوجّه شكرنا العميق لجميع العلماء الذين أسهموا في هذا المؤتمر، وللفرق الأكاديمية والإدارية التي شاركت في تنظيمه، ولكل من يضع التعليم في صدارة اهتماماته. ونأمل أن يكون هذا الكتاب مرجعًا قيمًا موجّهًا للبحوث التربوية المستقبلية.

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25/12/2024

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Bu belge, güvenli elektronik imza ile imzalanmıştır.

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Tunisian Parents' Roles as Listeners in Their Children's Sharing of Negative School Memories: A Qualitative Study with Tunisian Youth

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Abstract

Due to a dramatic lack of literature on autobiographical memory-sharing in the Tunisian context, this qualitative study replicates our prior research conducted with Turkish participants. It aims to explore (1) the perceived Functions of Sharing Negative Memories and (2) the characteristics of preferred and unpreferred listeners, specifically when parents serve as listeners to their emerging adult children's negative school experiences in Tunisia. The negative memories of Tunisian emerging adult children were instructed to be limited to the school setting to maintain narrative homogeneity. Using semi-structured interviews with 10 Tunisian participants, the data were fully transcribed and rigorously analyzed following Braun and Clarke's six-phase thematic analysis framework. The study identified both similarities and differences compared to the original Turkish sample. Directive functions were the most commonly reported. Additionally, self-functions were associated with fathers as listeners, while emotion regulation functions were linked to mothers. When serving as listeners, Tunisian mothers were preferred for their empathy and emotional closeness (relationship closeness), whereas Tunisian fathers were preferred for offering logical advice. Fathers may be unpreferred listeners due to perceived harsh criticism and emotional distance (relationship distance), while mothers may be unpreferred mainly due to being frequently distracted. Findings are discussed in light of the literature grounded in the Tunisian cultural context.

Keywords: Autobiographical memory-sharing, Functions of autobiographical memory, Perceived listener characteristics, Tunisian parents, Tunisian cultural context

Introduction

Autobiographical memory refers to an individual's recollection of personal life events and experiences. It includes both positive and negative specific episodic memories, as well as self-related knowledge, contributing to the formation of identity and a sense of self-continuity across time, linking the past, present, and future selves (Williams & Broadbent, 2007). When such memories are recalled and shared, they become autobiographical narratives, structured, personal stories that individuals construct and communicate to interpret their past experiences. These narratives play a vital role in shaping identity and often mirror culturally embedded values (Habermas & Bluck, 2000).

Emerging evidence indicates that reminiscing and sharing personal memories are common and recurrent activities in daily life. People often recall and share emotionally significant autobiographical memories, both positive and negative, through everyday social interactions (Pociunaite et al., 2023). Individuals engage in reminiscing and memory-sharing to fulfill certain functions in day-to-day life, which typically converge on three pivotal lifespan functions of autobiographical memory: the self function (e.g., fostering self-integrity), the social function (e.g., communication and bonding), and the directive function (e.g., guiding future behavior) (Bluck & Alea, 2002; Pillemer, 1992). These functions

often vary depending on the emotional valence of the memory. For example, negative memories are more frequently shared for directive (Rasmussen & Berntsen, 2009) and emotion regulation (Zaneti & Boyacıoğlu, 2025) purposes.

Moreover, in examining how negative experiences shape personal narratives, McAdams (2011) emphasizes that people often reminisce about negative events as a way to reflect on themselves and interpret their lives through a moral lens. This reflective process plays a key role in shaping one's identity as a moral individual. This supports the idea that life stories play a crucial role in forming and maintaining a moral sense of self (Strohming & Nichols, 2014).

The functions of autobiographical memory underscore the importance of understanding why people share their memories (Bruce, 1989), highlighting the need to study memory use in everyday life beyond its cognitive processes. To fully understand how people engage in memory sharing, especially when dealing with emotionally intense experiences, research must adopt a comprehensive framework. Such an approach should consider the broader conversational and relational contexts in which an individual chooses to disclose a memory to a particular listener. In fact, while people often feel inclined to narrate emotionally salient memories, it's evident that not all experiences are shared socially (Nils & Rimé, 2012). The expected reaction of the listener significantly influences whether a person chooses to share certain life events. Although individuals may refrain from disclosing certain autobiographical memories depending on the perceived receptiveness of the listener (Pasupathi et al., 2015), they are more likely to confide in those whom they expect to respond with empathy, attentiveness, and supportive engagement (Hoyt, Renshaw, & Pasupathi, 2013).

In this context, studies indicate that people often share their memories with those close to them, such as family members and friends (e.g., Alea & Bluck, 2003; Rimé et al., 1992). This preference to familiar listeners is attributed to the trust and understanding inherent in these relationships, which facilitate open and meaningful exchanges (Chen et al., 2016; Pasupathi, 2001).

Over the past twenty years, research has emphasized the critical role of listeners' characteristics in the context of autobiographical memory-sharing. When listeners are perceived with positive characteristics such as emotionally engaged, empathetic, and cooperative, they tend to shape the narrator's storytelling in meaningful ways, affecting not only the structure and depth of the narrative but also the narrator's emotional well-being and self-concepts (e.g., Pasupathi et al., 2015; Zaneti et al., 2025). Differences in how listeners respond can produce varying psychological outcomes. That is, positive characteristics of listening may foster healing, emotional relief, and social connectedness, while listeners' negative characteristics, such as indifference and distraction, often fail to generate these positive effects (Nils & Rimé, 2012).

The current study is a replication of our previous research, conducted in 2024 with a Turkish sample, which aimed to explore how Turkish parents are perceived as listeners in their children's sharing of negative autobiographical memories (Zaneti & Boyacıoğlu, under review). The primary aim of the study was to fill gaps in the examination of parents' listening role, rather than their narrating and scaffolding roles, in the context of family narratives. Seemingly, this replication aims to help fill the same gap in the literature, particularly within the Tunisian scientific context. We opted to replicate the same study in a different culture, focusing on the listening role of Tunisian parents in the context of their children's negative memory sharing, as autobiographical memory is deeply influenced by cultural patterns (e.g., Fivush & Nelson, 2004). Moreover, this replication is grounded in two primary motivations.

First, there is a notable gap in the Tunisian psychological literature concerning autobiographical memory, particularly from social and developmental perspectives. Consequently, Tunisian research examining the listener's role in memory sharing is absent, and studies comparing maternal and paternal influences within this context are also dramatically lacking.

Second, we chose to replicate the original study conducted with a Turkish sample using a Tunisian sample, due to the potential parallels in their ongoing cultural transitions. Indeed, Turkey has often been described as a society transitioning from traditional collectivism toward an "autonomous-related" self-construal, where autonomy and relatedness are integrated (Kagitcibasi, 2007). This cultural transformation has had a significant impact on family structures and parental roles, particularly in child-rearing (Gedik, 2020). In parallel, Tunisia has historically been classified as a collectivist culture (Yahyaoui & Zoubir, 2006; Omrane & Khan, 2024); however, like Turkey, it has undergone notable sociocultural changes in recent decades (Hermassi, 2020). These transformations have impacted family life, including the evolution of paternal and maternal roles (Maffi, 2017). Tunisian sociologist Hedia Bahloul describes contemporary fathers as in transition—caught between the traditional patriarchal figure and a modern paternal identity that embraces gender equality in parenting (Ben Nasser, 2024). A statement echoes Gedik's (2020) conclusions regarding contemporary Turkish fathers' struggle between 'the new fatherhood' and 'the traditional fatherhood' codes. Furthermore, growing evidence suggests that Tunisia, traditionally a collectivist society, is now experiencing a cultural shift toward more individualistic orientations due to globalization, urbanization, and changing family dynamics (Omrane & Khan, 2024; Van Assche et al., 2024). Given these parallels, the present study seeks to examine whether the memory-sharing dynamics in the family context identified in Turkey, particularly in the context of changing family roles, can also be observed in a Tunisian sample, thereby exploring the cultural generalizability of previous findings.

Operationally, the present study explores the sharing of negative autobiographical memories within familial relationships, focusing on Tunisian emerging adults recounting their negative school memories to their parents. The research seeks to understand how participants perceive their parents' listening characteristics and what purposes these memory-sharing experiences fulfill. Particular emphasis is placed on the preference for one parent as a listener over the other, as well as on the avoidance of sharing with a particular parent. The investigation aims to clarify the characteristics that define both preferred and unpreferred listeners, as perceived by the participants, and to analyze the expected functions underlying the decision to share negative memories with either the mother or the father.

Summarily, this qualitative study examines both (1) the perceived functions of sharing negative memories with the preferred Tunisian parent, as well as (2) the perceived characteristics of preferred and unpreferred listeners among Tunisian parents, mothers, and fathers, as described by their emerging adult children.

Methodology

To maintain fidelity to the original work being replicated, the present study adopted the same qualitative design. This choice was dictated by the nature of the variables examined, which required an in-depth exploration of personal experiences and subjective meanings.

Data were collected during June 2025 through individual interviews with 10 Tunisian emerging adults. The sample included four men and six women, aged between 19 and 24 years (see Table 2). Recruitment was based on convenience sampling: potential participants were initially contacted via phone, and the invitation to participate was further circulated within the researchers' professional and personal networks, reaching participants from different regions of Tunisia. Before agreeing to participate, all volunteers received detailed information about the study's goals and procedures and provided informed consent, with particular reassurance about anonymity and confidentiality.

Interviews were conducted online using Zoom and followed a semi-structured format. The guiding questions were deliberately open-ended, allowing participants to elaborate freely on their experiences, while additional probing questions were used when clarification or elaboration was needed. Each session lasted approximately 30 minutes. The interviews began with a reminder of the study's purpose and the assurance of confidentiality, followed by a brief demographic survey (age, gender, level of education, and place of residence).

Participants were then asked to recall and describe a negative personal memory that had occurred within the school setting within the last six months. They were asked to specify which of their parents they shared this memory with, as well as which parent they generally turn to for sharing such experiences. Participants were further invited to reflect on whether this choice of listener tends to remain stable over time. Subsequent questions explored their perceptions of the reasons and functions behind sharing these memories, as well as the characteristics they attributed to both their preferred and unpreferred listeners among their parents (see Table 2).

The material was examined through a combination of thematic analysis and interpretative phenomenological analysis, allowing both inductive and deductive insights to emerge. This dual strategy aimed to capture two dimensions of the data: (1) the functions attributed to sharing negative memories with a parent and (2) the characteristics associated with parents identified as preferred versus unpreferred listeners.

All interviews were fully transcribed and subjected to a rigorous analytic procedure. Following the six steps of thematic analysis described by Braun and Clarke (2006), the researcher got familiarized with the data through repeated readings, generated initial codes independently, and searched for patterns across the dataset. Themes were then refined, clearly defined, and named before compiling the final report. At the final step, coding was finalized.

The present study, as well as the original research it replicates, employed Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis due to its methodological flexibility and theoretical adaptability. This approach is well-suited for exploring subjective experiences and meaning-making processes, particularly within social and psychological contexts. Thematic analysis enables systematic identification, analysis, and interpretation of patterns within qualitative data, while allowing researchers to work within diverse epistemological frameworks. Its structured six-phase process offers a clear and rigorous guide. Moreover, its effectiveness has been supported in prior psychological research addressing autobiographical narratives (e.g., Ascienzo et al., 2022), making it particularly suitable for the current investigation.

While the original study focused specifically on negative autobiographical memories related to feelings of guilt, the present replication adopts a broader approach by including negative memories of any kind, regardless of whether the participant was in the role of victim or perpetrator. To ensure narrative homogeneity, only memories that occurred within the past six months and within the school context were considered. To explore the dynamics of negative memory-sharing within Tunisian families, where parents serve as listeners and emerging adult children as narrators, we employed a similar set of interview questions utilized in the original study. The questions were posed in Tunisian Arabic, commonly known as Derja, to ensure cultural and linguistic relevance within the Tunisian context.

1. Can you recall a recent negative event from the past six months that happened in school setting and that you shared with one of your parents?
2. Could you briefly describe this negative experience?
3. Which parent did you choose to talk to about this event, and what influenced your decision to speak with this parent instead of the other?
4. Do you generally tend to share such memories with the same parent? If yes, what drives this preference, and why is the other parent less likely to be chosen?
5. When it comes to negative memories, do you consistently choose the same parent to talk to? What explains this pattern?
6. Can you explain why you tend not to select the other parent as a listener in these situations?

7. When you confide in your chosen parent, what kind of response or support do you expect? What role or function do you hope they will provide while listening to your story?

These questions aim to prompt participants to reflect deeply on their experiences of sharing negative school memories, with a focus on how they perceive the roles and functions of each parent as listeners, and what characteristics make one parent more preferred than the other.

Results and Discussion

The initial analysis of the transcribed interviews revealed that participants' negative school memories clustered into four distinct thematic categories, based on the subjects involved in the conflicts. Specifically, the narratives were grouped into: (1) conflicts with classmates or dorm-mates, (2) conflicts with professors or lecturers, (3) conflicts with administrative personnel, and (4) conflicts with other students outside their class (see Table 1).

Table 1 presents these four narrative themes alongside representative examples from participants' recollections, provided in both the original language (Tunisian Derja) and their corresponding English translations.

Table 1: Thematic Categories of Participants' Negative School Memories with Representative Narrative Examples from Each Category

Categories of Narrative Themes	Examples of Negative School Memories Narrated in the Original Language (Tunisian Derja)	The English Version of the Narrated Negative School Memories
1. Conflicts with classmates/dorm-mates	"نهار من نهارات القراية، كنا نخدمو على بروجي مع بعضنا، ولاحظت اللي صاحبي في القروب ما يعمل في حتى شي، وبالرغم من هذا حب يحط اسمو هو اللول في البريزنتاسيون. كي حكيت معاه بالسياسة، تقلق وبدا يتهم فيا اللي نحب نتحكم. ولات عركة قدام باقي القروب. حسيت بالغصة وتقهت، خاصة كي حتى حد ما تدخل. الحكاية هادي خلاتني نفقد الثقة في خدمة القروب."	"One day during a group project, I realized my classmate wasn't contributing at all, yet kept insisting on putting his name first on the presentation. When I confronted him politely, he got defensive and accused me of being controlling. It escalated into a heated argument in front of the group. I felt frustrated and unsupported, especially when others stayed silent. It made me lose trust in teamwork for a while."
2. Conflicts with professors/lecturers	"صار بيني وبين الأستاذ مشكل على وقت تسليم البروجي. طلبت منه يمددلي المهلة بسبب ظروف شخصية تعديت بيها، لكنه تترفز عليا موش نورمال محسوب سبني قدام الطلبة قبل المحاضرة. حشمت ياسر ووليت ماعادش حابا. نحضرو المحاضرة"	"I had a disagreement with one of my professors about a project deadline. I asked for an extension due to personal issues, but he refused and criticized me harshly in front of the class. It made me feel embarrassed and discouraged, and I struggled to attend his lectures afterward."
3. Conflicts with administrative personnel	"وقت التسجيل، اتهموني بالغالط إني قدمت الأوراق متأخرة. رغم الدليل اللي عندي، الى يخدموا في الإدارة ما سمعوني وش وعاملوني بطريقة خابية ياسر. أنا تترفزت برشة ورديت بعنف، واللي تكلفتني غالية واضطريت نعلم دارنا بالموضوع"	"During registration, I was incorrectly accused of submitting documents late. Despite proof, the administrative staff ignored me and treated me badly. Frustrated, I reacted aggressively, which caused serious consequences, and I had to involve my parents."

4. Conflicts with other students (not classmates)	" في إيفينمون في الجامعة، صار لي مشكل كبير مع طلبة من ديبارتمون آخر. اتهموني ظلم على إني نيزنس في صاحبة واحد صاحبهم، رغم إنه مش صحيح. كثر الحكاية فيسع وصار بوذيل كبير وكالات بعضها بين الديبارتمنتات."	"During a campus event, I got into a serious argument with students from another department. They unfairly accused me of being involved with one guy's girlfriend, even though it wasn't true. The situation escalated quickly, causing a big scene and tension between departments."
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Tunisian Emerging Adult Children's Perceptions of the Functions of Sharing Negative Memories with Their Parents

This study explores everyday autobiographical memory exchanges within Tunisian families, guided by the ecological perspective on memory (Berntsen & Rubin, 2012; Bluck & Alea, 2002). The ecological approach of autobiographical memory views memories as serving adaptive functions within everyday social contexts. This model emphasizes that memory is not just about recalling facts but is purposefully used in daily life, particularly during memory-sharing moments, to fulfill these functions (Bluck & Alea, 2002). Consequently, this study focuses on emotionally significant memories related to negative events that have occurred at school within the past six months. These narratives were shared by Tunisian emerging adults with either their mothers or fathers. These inclusion criteria regarding the narrated experiences were deliberately chosen to maximize homogeneity among participants' narratives. Through in-depth interviews, participants reflected on these personal episodes, providing insight into the functions they perceived their parents fulfilled in response to their disclosures. The study analyzes these interviews qualitatively to uncover the perceived functions of negative memory-sharing in parent-child interactions.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 10 Tunisian emerging adults (4 males and 6 females). The data revealed that the majority of participants (7 out of 10) preferred to disclose negative personal experiences to their mothers, while the remaining 3 participants reported a preference for disclosing them to their fathers.

Moreover, all participants reported consistently disclosing their negative memories to the same preferred parent, suggesting a stable listener preference. This finding indicates that individuals not only make intentional choices about whom they disclose emotionally significant experiences to (Pasupathi et al., 2015) but also demonstrate loyalty and continuity in these sharing dynamics over time.

Qualitative analysis of the interview transcripts revealed three core perceived functions of negative autobiographical memory-sharing within the Tunisian parent-child dyad: directive, emotion-regulation, and self functions. Among these, the directive function emerged as the most frequently cited ($n = 8$), irrespective of the parent's gender. The emotion-regulation function was referenced by 4 participants and appeared in narratives involving mothers as listeners. In contrast, the self function, reported by 2 participants, was associated with memory-sharing experiences in which fathers served as listeners. These findings point to possible gender-based patterns in the perceived roles of parental listeners, suggesting that emerging adults may engage differently with mothers and fathers when seeking support to process negative life experiences (see Table 2).

Directive function

Tunisian emerging adults in this study predominantly emphasized the directive function of sharing negative personal experiences with their parents, irrespective of whether the listener was the mother or the father. This pattern mirrors findings from the original research conducted with Turkish

participants, where similar preferences for directive functions emerged, particularly when discussing negative memories associated with feelings of guilt (Zaneti & Boyacıoğlu, under review). The tendency for negative memories to serve a problem-solving or guidance-oriented purpose is well-documented in the literature (e.g., Pillemer, 2003; Burnell et al., 2020). According to these scholars, negative autobiographical recollections are more likely than positive ones to serve a directive function by offering insight for handling present or future challenges. In line with Bluck and Alea's conceptualization (2002), several participants described turning to a preferred parent as a listener to draw lessons from past difficulties to navigate current life situations. Their narratives correspond with the definition of the directive function as articulated by Raeder et al. (2019), in which memory sharing acts as a cognitive tool for coping with and resolving personal problems.

(P2) "My mom listens to help me deal with problems. I always leave the conversation not only feeling better, but also knowing what steps to take."

(P3) "I share with her my issues so she provides me with tips on how to deal with the situation."

(P4) "When it comes to negative experiences in life, confiding in my dad helps me see the situation more rationally and deal with it appropriately."

(P5) "When something goes wrong, I tell my mom because she always knows what I should do next."

(P7) "She offers guidance. It's like I get comfort and a plan at the same time."

(P8) "Whenever I share with him my problems, he orients me on how to solve things and make up for my mistakes."

(P9) "I talk to my mother when I'm lost or confused about what to do. She helps me decide on a plan."

(P10) "I always prefer to share my experience with my father because he succeeds in reminding me of my values and how I usually deal with things. It feels like he helps me reconnect with who I really am and how I should act."

Emotion-regulation and self-functions

In addition to the predominantly reported directive function, participants also identified emotion-regulation and self-functions, though these were reported less frequently. Notably, unlike the directive function, the perception of emotion regulation and self-functions appeared to be influenced by the gender of the parent. Specifically, participants who preferred their fathers as listeners were more likely to associate the memory-sharing experience with self-related functions, whereas those who preferred their mothers tended to emphasize emotion-regulation functions.

Participants' references to the emotion-regulation function ($n = 4$) are consistent with previous research, which indicates that individuals often retrieve or share autobiographical memories to cope with their emotions, improve their mood, and achieve emotional recovery (e.g., Nourkova & Gofman, 2022; Pasupathi et al., 2022). Sharing emotionally charged and negative everyday experiences with others serves important functions, such as helping individuals manage their emotions. This highlights how autobiographical memory operates functionally in daily life (Bluck & Alea, 2002). Consistent with this idea, Burnell, Coleman, and Hunt (2020) found that recalling negative autobiographical experiences can serve adaptive functions by aiding emotional processing and offering therapeutic benefits. The therapeutic and recovery-oriented dimensions of sharing negative memories, particularly with mothers, were evident in participants' narratives, as illustrated by expressions such as "emotional relief" (P1) and "she's my therapist" (P6), reflecting the perceived emotional comfort and support derived from these interactions.

The tendency of participants to perceive more emotion-regulation functions when sharing negative memories with their mothers, rather than fathers, is consistent with previous literature highlighting the central role of maternal figures in the development and support of children's emotional well-being. Research has shown that mothers are often more emotionally available and responsive, creating a supportive environment that facilitates emotion regulation in their children (Keleş & Çelik, 2024). Tan and Smith (2018) investigated the transmission of emotion regulation from mothers to their children. Scholars emphasize that caregivers, especially mothers, can provide an emotionally conducive climate in which children learn to manage their emotional experiences effectively (Tan & Smith, 2018). Supporting this pattern in the Arab cultural context, Agbaria (2017) found that children's emotion-regulation abilities were strongly associated with the quality of their mothers' attachment and the parenting style they adopted. Collectively, these findings may contribute to explaining why Tunisian emerging adults in this study attributed emotion-regulation functions to their mothers more frequently than to their fathers during memory-sharing experiences.

(P1) "I resort to mom to confide my negative experience in because she makes me feel better; it is a sort of emotional relief."

(P2) "I always leave the conversation not only feeling better..."

(P6) "When I'm overwhelmed, I talk to my mom because just speaking to her calms me down. She's my therapist. Well, she doesn't always fix the problem, but she makes me feel better, which is the most important to me. She always knows how to soothe me."

(P7) "I turn to my mother because she helps me process the emotion first, she's very soothing..."

Table 2: Demographic Information of Tunisian Emerging Adults and the Content of Their Perceived Functions of Sharing Negative Memories with Their Mothers and Fathers

Participant	Gender	Age	Residence place	Preferred listener's gender	Perceived functions of sharing negative memories	Example of content regarding perceived functions of sharing negative memories
1	Female	22	Rural	Mother	Emotion-regulation	I resort to mom to confide my negative experience in because she makes me feel better; it is a sort of emotional relief.
2	Male	24	Urban	Mother	Directive + Emotion-regulation	My mom listens to help me deal with problems and feel relieved. I always leave the conversation not only feeling better, but also knowing what steps to take.
3	Male	21	Urban	Mother	Directive	I share with her my issues so she provides me with tips on how to deal with the situation.
4	Female	24	Rural	Father	Directive + Self	When it comes to negative experiences in life, confiding in my dad makes me see the situation more rationally. It helps me organize my thoughts and understand the situation and myself better.
5	Female	22	Metropolitan	Mother	Directive	When something goes wrong, I tell my mom because she always knows what I should do next.
6	Female	21	Urban	Mother	Emotion-regulation	When I'm overwhelmed, I talk to my mom because just speaking to her calms me down. She's my therapist. Well, she doesn't always fix the problem, but she makes me feel better, which is the most important to me. She always knows how to soothe me.
7	Male	23	Urban	Mother	Directive + Emotion-regulation	I turn to my mother because she helps me process the emotion first, she's very soothing, and then she offers guidance. It's like I get comfort and a plan at the same time.
8	Female	20	Rural	Father	Directive	Whenever I share with him my problems, he orients me how to solve things and make up my mistakes.
9	Female	19	Metropolitan	Mother	Directive	I talk to my mother when I'm lost or confused about what to do. She helps me decide on a plan.
10	Male	19	Metropolitan	Father	Directive + Self	I always prefer to share my experience with my father because I know he succeeds in reminding me of my values and how I usually deal with things. It feels like he is able to make me reconnect with who I really am.

The identification of self functions in the sharing of negative autobiographical memories supports the existing literature, which highlights the adaptive role that such memories can play in shaping the self (Burnell et al., 2020). Prior research suggests that recalling and narrating negative experiences allows individuals to reflect on their personal growth and evolving identity over time (Rasmussen & Berntsen, 2009; Williams et al., 2022). Within the framework of autobiographical memory, this process

contributes to the construction and reinforcement of the self by enabling individuals to make sense of difficult events and integrate them into a coherent life narrative (Bluck & Alea, 2002; Bluck et al., 2005).

(P4) “It helps me organize my thoughts and understand the situation and myself better.”

(P10) “I always prefer to share my experience with my father because he succeeds in reminding me of my values and how I usually deal with things. It feels like he helps me reconnect with who I really am.”

The association between the self-function of negative memory-sharing and fathers rather than mothers has been observed in previous research (e.g., Zaneti et al., 2025). For example, a Turkish study found that fathers exert a stronger influence on children’s self-perceptions compared to mothers (Sümer & Şendağ, 2009). Similarly, Dwairy (2006), in his book *Counseling and Psychotherapy with Arabs and Muslims: A Culturally Sensitive Approach*, highlights the paternal role in fostering children’s self-development in Arab cultures. He explains that, in traditional Arab societies, the father typically embodies authority and discipline, which significantly shapes the child’s development of self-control and identity. By setting expectations, boundaries, and moral standards, fathers play a crucial role in shaping the child’s understanding of social norms and the development of their moral self.

Perceived Characteristics of the Preferred and Unpreferred listeners among Tunisian parents

The literature on the role of listeners in autobiographical memory-sharing generally shows that the listener’s characteristics significantly impact both the content of the narrative and the narrator’s experience, whether in a positive or negative direction. Most studies investigating this question employ an experimental design in which researchers manipulate the characteristics or behavior of the listener and then ask narrators, who are the study participants, to rate the perceived characteristics of the listener (e.g., Pasupathi & Rich, 2005; Pasupathi et al., 2007). Findings from these studies consistently demonstrate that positive listener characteristics, such as attentiveness, cooperativeness, and empathy, enhance the narrative content and contribute to the narrator’s emotional well-being. In contrast, negative listener characteristics, such as being distracted, indifferent, or uncooperative, tend to negatively impact both the structure and emotional valence of the shared memory (Pasupathi et al., 2015).

The present study, in line with the original research it replicates, aims to explore listener characteristics as perceived naturally by narrators in everyday life, without any manipulation or instruction given to the listener. More specifically, it examines the characteristics that lead narrators to select certain individuals, particularly within the family context, as preferred recipients of their negative memory disclosures, as well as the characteristics that explain why they avoid others. In this framework, both preferred and unpreferred listener profiles are examined, with a focus on the role of Tunisian parents as listeners and their emerging adult children as narrators. This approach allows for a more ecological and culturally grounded understanding of listener preferences. It also enables the emergence of naturally occurring descriptors of listener characteristics, reflecting how memory-sharing unfolds in real-life Tunisian family sharings.

The results revealed that participants’ perceptions of what makes a parent a preferred or unpreferred listener are shaped by the parent’s gender. When describing why they favored their mothers as listeners, participants frequently highlighted two main factors: their mothers’ empathetic responses and the emotional closeness shared in their close relationship. In contrast, when fathers were identified as the preferred listeners, participants primarily valued their ability to offer practical and logical advice. Distinctions also emerged in how participants described the qualities that made a parent less preferable as a confidant. Fathers were often seen as less suitable due to two consistent reasons: their harsh criticism and a lack of emotional closeness (an overall distance in their relationships). On the other hand, mothers were generally perceived as less ideal listeners when they appeared distracted during conversations (see Table 3).

Table 3: Tunisian emerging adults' perceived characteristics of preferred vs. unpreferred listeners among their mothers and fathers

Parents' gender as a listener	Perceived characteristics of the preferred listener	Perceived characteristics of the unpreferred listener
Father	Logical advice	Relationship distance (Emotional distance)
		Harsh criticism
Mother	Relationship closeness (Emotional intimacy)	Distraction
	Empathy	

Perceived characteristics of the preferred listener between Tunisian mothers and fathers

The findings of the present study indicate that the majority of Tunisian participants reported a preference for disclosing their negative autobiographical memories to their mothers rather than their fathers. Additionally, all participants, regardless of the gender of their preferred listener, demonstrated consistent loyalty to the same confidant over time, reinforcing the idea that individuals make deliberate choices about whom they confide in (Pasupathi et al., 2015). Similarly, a preference for mothers over fathers in the context of children's negative memory-sharing was also observed in the original study conducted with a Turkish sample (Zaneti & Boyacıoğlu, under review).

When the preferred listeners were Tunisian mothers, one salient characteristic frequently attributed to them was the perceived relationship closeness and emotional intimacy they provide. These observations align with recent findings indicating that, regardless of their educational attainment or economic contributions, mothers in Tunisia continue to be the primary caregivers. They spend substantially more time in close interaction with their children than fathers do (El Lahga & Amara, 2020; Nazier & Ezzat, 2022). A plausible explanation for these findings lies in the pervasive societal stereotypes that structure family roles, portraying mothers as more engaged in child-rearing than fathers across Arab countries (e.g., Dwairy, 2006). Dwairy (2006) highlighted that in Arab societies, mothers are regarded as the central figures in children's upbringing, carrying the primary responsibility for emotional nurturing and daily caregiving. This division of roles reflects deeply rooted cultural expectations and societal norms that assign caregiving responsibilities according to gender.

In addition to the category of emotional intimacy and relationship closeness, empathy emerged as the second most salient perceived characteristic of preferred listeners when mothers were identified as the preferred confidants. This perception of maternal empathy was also reflected in the findings of the original study conducted with Turkish youth, in which participants similarly reported a preference for confiding in their mothers due to their empathic listening (Zaneti & Boyacıoğlu, under review). These findings are consistent with the work of Pasupathi and Rich (2005), who argue that empathic listening plays a crucial role in positively influencing the narrators and their experiences of autobiographical memory-sharing.

Moreover, the observed tendency to associate empathy more strongly with maternal rather than paternal listening aligns with existing literature suggesting that women are generally more empathic than men (Baez et al., 2017; Geary, 2002). This gender-based difference in empathic responsiveness is further supported by research from Tunisia. A recent study aimed at validating the Basic Empathy Scale for Children (BESC) within the Tunisian context revealed that, even from an early age, Tunisian girls demonstrate higher levels of empathic responsiveness compared to boys (Ben Youssef et al., 2022). These findings provide additional cultural and developmental grounding for understanding why maternal empathy may play a key role in autobiographical memory-sharing dynamics within Tunisian families.

Participants who identified their fathers as their preferred listeners for disclosing negative personal experiences consistently emphasized a particular perceived characteristic: the tendency of Tunisian fathers to offer logical, solution-oriented advice. This recurring theme closely mirrors findings from the original study conducted with Turkish participants, where similar perceptions of paternal listening styles were reported (Zaneti & Boyacıoğlu, under review). These findings resonate with Gray's (1992) theoretical perspective on gendered communication styles, which highlights that men often adopt a results-driven, task-oriented mode of interaction, whereas women are more inclined toward relational and emotionally supportive communication. This distinction was also reflected in participant narratives from the current study, particularly in instances where fathers were described as steering conversations toward immediate problem-solving and avoiding what some participants perceived as unnecessary or overly emotional dialogue (see P8). The tendency to seek emotional support and empathy from mothers, but pragmatic advice from fathers, reflects culturally embedded gender roles in parenting, where mothers are often expected to nurture emotional bonds. In contrast, fathers are seen as providers of advice or problem solvers in Arab cultures, such as Tunisia (Dwairy, 2006). This division of roles may be reinforced by societal expectations in Tunisia and broader Arab societies, where fathers traditionally assume a more authoritarian and guiding role, particularly in decision-making domains (Hermassi, 2020). While mothers are typically perceived as more emotionally accessible, fathers may be viewed as more rational and experienced, especially in situations requiring judgment, discipline, or planning. This functional differentiation in parental support suggests that Tunisian emerging adult children may internalize distinct emotional and cognitive roles for each parent, influencing how they navigate emotional disclosure within the family context.

Fathers: Logical advice provision

(P8) "What I appreciate most in my father's listening is his appropriate feedback based on rational logic. He is very pragmatic-minded, which is exactly what I need when I'm in trouble. I hate emotion-based plans; they are a real waste of time. In such situations, all I need is an action-based plan, which I consistently find when confiding in my dad rather than my mom".

Mothers: Empathy

(P2) "I love confiding in my mom because I truly see her empathy. No matter what I mess up, she always seems empathetic toward me".

Mothers: Relationship closeness (Emotional intimacy)

(P7) "I definitely prefer my mom because she is simply closer to me than my dad. My relationship with her is much more intimate compared to the one I have with my father. I share everything with my mother, including both my positive and negative life experiences. The nature of our bond is incomparable to my bond with my dad. She is emotionally closer to all of us, not just me".

Perceived characteristics of the unpreferred listener between Tunisian mothers and fathers

A number of participants indicated inhibition in confiding their negative personal experiences to their Tunisian fathers, largely due to a perceived pattern of harsh criticism and a sense of emotional and relational distance. This perception of paternal criticism mirrors findings from the original study, where Turkish participants similarly reported avoiding disclosure to their fathers because of their critical responses (Znaeti & Boyacıoğlu, under review). When viewed together, the perceived harshness and emotional distance of Tunisian fathers, as well as the emotional closeness attributed to Tunisian mothers, align with patterns documented in prior research on Tunisian family dynamics and cultural norms. Previous research highlights the predominance of authoritarian parenting in Arab and North African societies, where obedience, discipline, and hierarchy are culturally valued (Dwairy et al., 2006). In these contexts, authoritarian practices, particularly by fathers, are often viewed not as harmful but as expressions of care and responsibility. Dwairy (1998a) noted that strictness and criticism are perceived as essential for instilling discipline and upholding family honor, while emotional distance is seen as reinforcing respect. Similarly, in Tunisia, such control is often associated with protection and the promotion of communal values (Dwairy, 2004). This division of parental roles aligns with Arab cultural norms where mothers offer emotional closeness, while fathers serve as authority figures and moral guides (Joseph, 1994). Historical evidence from Tunisia suggests that father–child relationships, particularly with daughters, were often emotionally distant in the 1960s and 1970s, reinforcing patterns of paternal detachment (Ben Salem et al., 2023). This dynamic persists today, with paternal authority expressed more through provision and moral oversight than emotional intimacy. Furthermore, in Tunisian and broader Arab cultures, masculinity is closely linked to strength, authority, and emotional restraint, discouraging men from expressing vulnerability. Boys are socialized early into “restrictive emotionality,” as emotional expression conflicts with cultural ideals of manhood (Dwairy et al., 2006). Fathers are expected to embody discipline and authority, while emotional openness is often reserved for mothers, thereby reinforcing traditional gender roles (Joseph, 1994). Arab men tend to suppress emotions, as showing weakness is seen as incompatible with the protector-provider role (Dwairy, 2010).

Participants who reported avoiding sharing their negative memories with their mothers attributed this to perceived undesired listener characteristics, primarily distractedness. This observation corroborates Pasupathi and Hoyt’s (2010) findings, which show that distracted listeners negatively affect narrators’ memories. Moreover, the association of distractedness with Tunisian mothers rather than fathers can be explained by recent Tunisian literature. Studies show that today, women in Tunisia bear a disproportionate share of unpaid domestic and care work, leading to chronic multitasking and time poverty. UN Women (2024) reports that Tunisian women (15 years and older) spend approximately 5.3 hours daily on unpaid care work, compared to just 0.6 hours for men. Econometric analyses confirm that women allocate significantly more time to caregiving and are more likely to experience time poverty (Nazier & Ezzat, 2022). These disparities reflect structural differences in workload between mothers and fathers in Tunisia. Research shows that such role overload contributes to strain, with Tunisian working women reporting increased anxiety and parental burnout during crises like COVID-19 (Guedria et al., 2023). Together, these findings suggest that Tunisian mothers engage in more multitasking and often face greater time constraints than Tunisian fathers, which may help explain why Tunisian emerging adult children perceive their mothers as more distracted during moments of disclosure.

Fathers: Harsh criticism

(P1) "I avoid confiding in my father because whenever I open up to him, he tends to highlight some flaw or shortcoming in me, which feels unnecessarily harsh. Even when I share my achievements, he somehow manages to find something to criticize. It’s as if he always focuses on what’s wrong with me rather than acknowledging what’s right".

Fathers: Relationship distance (Emotional distance)

(P9) "Well, I don't prefer sharing my emotional stories with him because my relationship with my father doesn't feel intimate enough. We are not close to each other, so honestly, I don't feel emotionally connected to him enough to share my emotional experiences".

Mothers: Distraction

(P4) "Whenever I turn to her to share something, even an ordinary political event occurring in Tunisia, not just personal experiences or plans, she is distracted by other chores such as cleaning or cooking, which gets on my nerves and makes me regret sharing anything with her".

Conclusion and Recommendations

The present study replicates our earlier research conducted in 2024 (Zaneti & Boyacıoğlu, under review) with a Turkish sample. It aims to address the significant gap in the Tunisian literature concerning everyday autobiographical memory-sharing from both social and developmental perspectives. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first empirical investigation specifically focused on the Tunisian context in this domain. Consequently, the limited availability of relevant scientific literature posed a notable challenge for interpreting the findings within Tunisia's cultural framework. Nonetheless, the results revealed novel, meaningful cross-cultural parallels. In both the Turkish and Tunisian contexts, the maternal figure emerged as the preferred confidant for sharing negative autobiographical experiences, highlighting culturally shared perceptions of mothers as emotionally accessible and empathic listeners, alongside fathers' relational and emotional distance as listeners within family dynamics.

Theoretically, these parallel findings are best understood through a cultural–historical lens that acknowledges both continuity and change in paternal roles. While parenting practices vary cross-culturally, functional divisions, mothers as emotional caregivers and fathers as instrumental or disciplinary figures, persist in traditionally patriarchal societies, such as Turkey (Gedik, 2020) and Tunisia (Ben Nasser, 2024). However, socio-economic modernization has led to critical transitional patterns: fathers in both countries are becoming more involved, yet still retain traditional traits of authority and emotional reserve. In this context, Tunisian sociologist Hedia Bahloul describes this shift as a transition caught between traditional and modern fatherhood (Ben Nasser, 2024). Similarly, the Turkish sociologist Gedik (2020) notes the same tensions in contemporary Turkish fatherhood. This evolving "in-between" role helps explain the perceived emotional distance and unavailability of fathers, despite their valued, logical advice when listening to their children. It also clarifies why mothers remain preferred listeners, even as fathers contribute more to caregiving. Methodologically, this replication highlights the value of cross-cultural comparison in autobiographical memory research by confirming core functions (emotion regulation, directive support) while revealing how cultural norms dictate which parent fulfills each. Practically, it suggests that improving father–child communication requires not only increased paternal involvement but also emotional support, alongside reducing mothers' heavy load to enable meaningful listening.

The results of this research provide meaningful implications for the educational sector. When children perceive a parent as a safe emotional container, they may be more willing to disclose academic worries or emotional stressors, facilitating interventions. Conversely, perceiving a parent as a logical advisor may encourage reflection on study strategies, time management, or problem-solving. Moreover, these observations have relevant implications for educational Psychology. Indeed, they may contribute to student counseling and interventions. Understanding that students may approach different parents depending on whether they need emotional processing or practical advice suggests that school counselors could involve those parents differently. For example, training mothers in active listening techniques may support students' emotional regulation, while engaging fathers in conversations about planning and academic feedback may enhance students' self-regulation outcomes. Furthermore, for parent involvement programs: Schools often encourage parental involvement primarily in academic or logistical tasks (homework support, meeting attendance); however, this research's findings suggest a

more nuanced approach: programs should also foster listening skills and sensitivity in parents, training in high-quality listening behaviors (non-distraction, empathy, logical advice) might strengthen home-school support networks. Similarly, for curriculum design, incorporating autobiographical sharing as a pedagogical tool (e.g., reflective assignments, narrative prompts) can invite students to reframe negative experiences, foster self-insight, and build relational empathy. Some educational texts suggest that autobiographical memory and future imaginings can help teachers and students bridge their personal experiences and subject matter (Hinchion, 2020).

Although qualitative research is not easily generalizable due to its typically small sample sizes, it provides rich and detailed insights into the studied phenomena, especially when exploring the nuanced dynamics of everyday life, where quantitative methods may risk oversimplification or bias. Indeed, this study provides novel insights into the perceived functions of sharing negative autobiographical memories within Tunisian families, revealing how children evaluate their parents as preferred or non-preferred listeners based on characteristics such as empathy, emotional closeness/distance, and distraction. By extending autobiographical memory research in Tunisia beyond its predominantly neuropsychological framing, the study addresses the scarcity of work on memory-sharing in Arab contexts, where parent-child communication is shaped by authority, gender norms, and cultural scripts. Findings reveal that children rely on parental responsiveness when selecting listeners, corroborating prior research on the role of listeners in this context (Pasupathi et al., 2015). Additionally, these observations influence both family cohesion and emotional adjustment, and demonstrate that autobiographical memory should be understood not only as a cognitive process but also as a relational practice embedded in parental roles. Beyond these theoretical contributions, applied implications emerge: memory sharing functions as a relational barometer of emotional availability, with perceptions of empathy, harshness, or distraction shaping whether children feel heard, supported, or silenced. International research has shown that parental responsiveness fosters socioemotional adjustment and identity (e.g., Fivush, Haden, & Reese, 2006) as well as self-concepts such as the child's self-compassion (Zaneti & Boyacıoğlu, 2025). At the same time, local cultural patterns, mothers' multitasking caregiving and fathers' authoritarian stance (harsh criticism), determine who is perceived as an effective listener. These results emphasize the need for culturally sensitive parenting interventions that promote empathetic listening and shared emotional responsibility, while also contributing culturally specific evidence to international memory research and advancing cross-cultural psychology by demonstrating how family roles and cultural expectations shape the relational use of autobiographical memory.

Obviously, the Tunisian literature on autobiographical memory, particularly from social and developmental perspectives, is still in what might be described, metaphorically, as the "oral phase" of its development: emerging, exploratory, and not yet consolidated into a mature research tradition. Most existing work has focused on neuropsychological, cognitive, and clinical dimensions of memory, leaving relational, cultural, and developmental aspects from an ecological perspective largely uncharted. This very early stage highlights the need for further empirical research, both qualitative and quantitative, to investigate how autobiographical memory functions within Tunisian family relationships and in daily life more broadly. Expanding this line of inquiry would not only enrich the Tunisian scientific literature but also provide a culturally grounded contribution to the broader international field of autobiographical memory.

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يشكل هذا الكتاب ثمرةً علمية قيّمة لـسيمنار المؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للمجتمع التربوي الذي انعقد في أنطاليا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، بتنسيق من مجموعة سايبيلدر ودعم أكاديمي من جامعتي ماردن أرنتوكلو (تركيا) وفرطاج (تونس). وقد جمع هذا الحدث نخبة من الباحثين من تركيا وأحد عشر بلداً آخر، مما أتاح فضاءً حيويًا لتبادل الخبرات ومناقشة قضايا التربية في سياقات متعددة.

يضم هذا الكتاب مجموعة من الأبحاث التي تناولت أحدث الاتجاهات في التعليم، من التكنولوجيا التربوية وتعليم اللغات إلى سياسات التعليم المستدام والإرشاد النفسي والتربية الخاصة. ولا يُعدّ مجرد تجميع لأوراق علمية، بل مرجعاً يعكس تنوع التجارب وتكامل الرؤى بين الباحثين.

نأمل أن يقدم هذا العمل إضافة نوعية للباحثين والممارسين، وأن يساهم في تعزيز جسور التعاون العلمي الدولي في ميدان التربية.

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